

Origin of the bright photoluminescence of few-atom silver clusters confined in LTA-zeolites

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Abstract

Silver clusters confined in matrices possess remarkable luminescence properties, but little is known about their structural and electronic properties. We characterized the bright green luminescence of Ag clusters confined in partially exchanged Ag-LTA-zeolites by a combination of X-ray Excited Optical Luminescence – Extended X-ray Absorption Fine Structure (XEOL-EXAFS), Time Dependent-Density Functional Theory (TD-DFT) calculations and time-resolved spectroscopy. A mixture of tetrahedral $\text{Ag}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_x^{2+}$ ($x=2$ & 4) clusters occupy the center of a fraction of the sodalite cages. Their optical properties originate from a confined two-electron super-atom quantum system with hybridized Ag and water O orbitals delocalized over the cluster. Upon excitation, one electron of the s-type highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) is promoted to the p-type lowest occupied molecular orbitals (LUMOs) and relaxes through enhanced system intercrossing into long-lived triplet states.

One Sentence Summary

The bright luminescence of Ag-LTA-zeolites originates from the long-lived triplet state of two-electron super-atom quantum systems confined in $\text{Ag}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ and $\text{Ag}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$ clusters.

Main text

Few-atom luminescent silver clusters (AgCLs) (1) stabilized by organic (e.g., peptides, proteins, polymers and DNA) (2-6) or inorganic (e.g., glasses and zeolites) (7-9) templates have emerged as promising candidates for a broad range of applications in lighting, imaging, sensing, and therapeutics. (4) Compared to conventional quantum dots, few-atom AgCLs combine an ultra-small size with excellent size-dependent photoluminescence (PL) spanning the ultraviolet to near-infrared spectrum. Strong quantum confinement of silver valence electrons appears to break up the continuous density of states into discrete energy levels and confer molecular-like properties to the AgCLs. Nevertheless, the lack of a detailed understanding of the fundamental photophysical mechanisms underlying their emissions is hampering the rational design of AgCLs with improved and tailored optical properties. Atomic structures for AgCLs have not been determined unambiguously because of their vast distribution of size, environment, and template interactions, as well as the presence of a large fraction of non-luminescent silver species.

The AgCLs that self-assemble in the cavities of the rigid aluminosilicate crystalline framework of zeolites have the most homogeneous and efficient emissions. The PL of AgCLs confined in thermally activated Ag loaded zeolite structures of FAU and LTA topologies features tunable absorption and emission, large Stokes shifts, and exceptionally high external quantum efficiencies (EQE's) reaching unity. (8, 10) However, the structure of these AgCLs has not been fully elucidated yet because of the complexity of silver-zeolite host-guest interactions and to the sensitivity of silver-zeolite composites toward radiation (electrons and photons) used in structural characterization techniques. (11) We present a detailed investigation of the structural and electronic properties of partially silver exchanged Ag_3K_9 -LTA zeolite using three complementary techniques. This system was selected for its green PL featuring an excellent EQY of 23% among the Ag-LTA zeolites, its good stability towards x-ray irradiation, (11) and its simpler crystallographic structure than FAU zeolites. We selectively determined the structure of the emitting silver species using XEOL to detect the EXAFS signal exclusively from the Ag atoms involved in the PL process at Ag K-edge. (12) The structures obtained experimentally were confirmed computationally by geometry optimizations using DFT methods, while TD-DFT was

applied to determine the electronic transitions responsible for the absorption and emission spectra of the stable isomers. Finally, to confirm the electronic structure of the theoretically modeled AgCLs, we identified the relevant decay modes and time scales involved in the absorption and luminescence processes of Ag₃K₉-LTA using a combination of femto- to millisecond time-resolved spectroscopies.

The large number of structural characterizations of AgCLs stabilized in LTA zeolites, often performed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) and electron spin resonance (ESR), (13-16) have led to numerous incomplete and often contradictory structural models. Ag₃₋₄ clusters were tentatively related to partially silver exchanged LTA zeolites, whereas Ag₆ clusters were associated to fully exchanged samples. In a recent study, high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) revealed octahedral Ag₆ clusters within the sodalite cages of fully exchanged Ag-LTA zeolites, (17) but no evidence linking the reported structure to the PL was provided. Similar analysis of partially exchanged Ag-LTA zeolites, remained unsuccessful due to the strong influence of electron-beam irradiation. (17, 18)

EXAFS (19) can provide information on cluster size and the atomic-scale bonding both for emissive and non-emissive clusters. (20) In contrast, XEOL exclusively detects the XAFS signal from the atoms constituting the emissive species (12, 21, 22). Also, while x-ray irradiation can affect the structure of few-atom clusters (11), XEOL would monitor any beam degradation effect (see Supplementary Materials). The 3D structures of the AgCLs were determined by combining the fitting results of the XEOL and transmission-detected EXAFS collected simultaneously (Table S1). We primarily analyzed the XEOL-detected EXAFS of Ag₃K₉-LTA. Fig. 1A and 1B show the $\chi(k)$ k^3 -weighted EXAFS data and the corresponding phase-corrected Fourier Transform (FT) best fits.

The first and second peaks of the FT were fitted with respectively 2 O atoms at 2.36 Å (N1) and 3 Ag atoms at 2.82 Å (N2). Additionally, the fit was completed with two longer shells consisting of 0.4 K at 3.05 Å (N4) and 1.1 Ag at 3.3 Å (N5). The Ag atoms coordinated to 3 other Ag atoms (Ag_C) form tetrahedral-like Ag₄ clusters located inside the sodalite cage, as was shown by TEM

(17) The Ag_C atoms are each coordinated to 2 oxygen atoms likely corresponding to extra-framework water molecules because of the short Ag-O distances (see Supplementary Materials).

Fig. 1. Ag K-edge XEOL and transmission-detected EXAFS and FTs of heat-treated Ag_3K_9 -LTA and derived structures. XEOL-detected k^3 -weighted EXAFS (A) with the phase corrected FT (B) best fits and Transmission-detected Ag K-edge k^3 -weighted EXAFS (C) with the phase corrected FT (D) best fits. Structures of $\text{Ag}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$ and $\text{Ag}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ (E and H), including Ag_R cations (F and I) and embedded in the sodalite cage (G and J) respectively.

The analysis of the XEOL-detected signal shows that the species at the origin of the bright green PL observed in Ag_3K_9 -LTA are Ag_4 clusters with short Ag-Ag distances of 2.82 Å in which each Ag atom is bound to 2 water molecules at 2.36 Å on average. They are further surrounded by isolated K and Ag cations likely positioned in the single six-membered rings (S6Rs) of the same sodalite cage. A twofold coordination of Ag_C atoms however does not correspond to an integer number of water molecules inside the cage but rather to two different stoichiometries of $x=2$ and $x=4$ corresponding to a water coordination of each Ag_C forming the cluster of 1.5 and 3 respectively. This analysis suggests the presence of a mixture of $\text{Ag}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$ and $\text{Ag}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ with a ca. 34/66 ratio ($3 \times 0.34 + 1.5 \times 0.66 = 2$) in this Ag_3K_9 -LTA sample (see below).

We also analyzed the transmission-detected EXAFS collected simultaneously with the XEOL-detected data. Fig. 1, C and D, shows the $\chi(k)$ k^3 -weighted EXAFS data and the phase-corrected FTs best fits of heat-treated Ag_3K_9 -LTA. The distinct profiles compared with those collected with

XEOL-detection indicate that two different average local environments of Ag atoms were measured simultaneously, which is consistent with the XANES analysis (see Supplementary Materials).

The first peak in the FT was fit with 2.5 O at 2.34 Å (N1) corresponding to the combination of the framework O (O_F) from the S6Rs rings and the H₂O ligands, as shown in the XEOL analysis. The second peak in the FT is a multiplex composed of 2.6 Si/Al atoms (N2) at 3.26-3.30 Å corresponding to a fraction of non-luminescent Ag cations located near the center of the S6Rs (henceforth referred as Ag_R) (Fig. S13), not detected in XEOL-EXAFS. The second peak in the FT analysis also contained a weaker Ag-Ag contribution (N3) of 1.7 Ag at unusually short distances of 2.70 Å. This feature corresponds to the remaining part of the silver atoms Ag_C (ca. 57%) that are coordinated to ca. 3 (1.7/0.57) silver neighbors and are forming Ag_4 clusters inside the sodalite cage. The 4% discrepancy between the Ag_C - Ag_C (2.70 Å to 2.82 Å) distances found by the two detection approaches suggests that XEOL measured preferentially the excited state structure of the clusters (see Supplementary Materials). Ag_C in Ag_4 CLs are coordinated to 2.1 O (1.2/0.57) from water molecules. Additionally, two shells consisting of K and Ag were detected between 2.97 and 4.46 Å corresponding to Ag_C -K or Ag_C - Ag_R distances associated with the absence or presence, respectively, of a water molecule sandwiched between the two atoms (Fig. S13).

The EXAFS investigation shows that the emitters in Ag_3K_9 -LTA consist of ca. 40 % of $Ag_4(H_2O)_4$ and 60 % of $Ag_4(H_2O)_2$ tetrahedral-like clusters located at the center of the sodalite cage. These structures are presented in Fig. 1, E to J. The clusters are coordinated at their faces by 2 or 4 water molecules located close to the center of the S6Rs and sandwiched between 3 Ag_C and one Ag_R (or K cation). Ag CLs consisting of 57% of the total number of exchanged Ag atoms are mostly surrounded by the remaining 43% isolated Ag_R cations plus some additional K cations in the S6Rs. A strong local concentration of Ag cations (6 to 7 Ag atoms instead of 3 expected from the Ag stoichiometry) occupies a limited fraction of the sodalite cages (ca. 45 %). (23)

We used a combination of DFT and TD-DFT to model Ag CLs, and probed their charges with the natural bonding orbital approach. Two stable isomers [$Ag_4(H_2O)_x(Si_{24}H_{24}O_{36})$] $x=2$ and $x=4$

showing the best agreement between calculated and measured structures and absorption spectra, were obtained when applying a +2 charge preferentially localized on the Ag₄CLs. The doubly charged Ag₄CLs exhibit a closed-shell electronic configuration, where the Ag 4d shell is completely filled and the two remaining valence 5s electrons were delocalized over the cluster. Within a super-atom model, two electrons associated to a metal cluster correspond to the smallest magic number with enhanced stability, (24, 25) consistent with analogous theoretical work on Ag₄CLs. (26),(27)

Both isomers (Ag₄(H₂O)_x, x=2 and 4) consist of pseudo tetrahedral Ag₄ clusters located in an off-centered position in the sodalite cage with one or two silver atoms coordinated directly to O_F (See Supplementary Materials and Fig. S14&S15). In Ag₄(H₂O)₄ each silver atom is coordinated on average to 2 oxygen atoms (water plus O_F) with an average Ag-Ag bond distance of ca. 2.79 Å and 2.92 Å in the ground and excited state respectively (Fig. S14). In Ag₄(H₂O)₂ an average Ag-Ag distance of 2.87 Å in the ground state and a mean O coordination close to 1.7 was obtained (Fig. S15). These calculated structures featuring a 5% increase in the Ag_C-Ag_C distances from the ground to the excited states are in good agreement with the experimental results (See Supplementary Materials).

The calculated frontier orbitals for both Ag₄(H₂O)₄²⁺ and Ag₄(H₂O)₂²⁺ isomers (Fig. 2A and S16 respectively) are composed of a contribution of ca. 50% from Ag 5s atomic orbitals and of up to 25% from the oxygen states of the surrounding O_F and H₂O, as shown in the density of states curves (Fig. S18). A doubly occupied ¹S₀ HOMO of totally symmetric s-type and two sets of three singlet ¹P and three triplet ³P LUMOs of p-type character with one node, form the expected lowest-lying cluster orbitals for a cluster system with two skeleton electrons. Both isomers have similar atomic orbital compositions (Fig. S18), suggesting that the excitations are mainly localized on the clusters.

Fig. 2. Frontier orbitals of $[\text{Ag}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(\text{Si}_{24}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_{36})]^{2+}$ and energy level diagram of $\text{Ag}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+}$ and $\text{Ag}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4^{2+}$ clusters in $\text{Ag}_3\text{K}_9\text{-LTA}$. (A) Frontier orbitals consist of one single symmetric s-type HOMO ($^1\text{S}_0$) and 3 singlet ones of node p-type ^1P ($m_l = -1, +1$ or 0) LUMOs (p_x, p_y, p_z) delocalized over all the silver and O atoms of the cluster. (Atom colors: Silicon=Grey; Oxygen=red; Silver=blue; Hydrogen=white). (B) Energy level diagram showing the ground state $^1\text{S}_0$ and the excited states ^3P and ^1P of water-free unperturbed Ag_4^{2+} clusters and the ground state $^1\text{S}_0$ and the six singlet ^1P and triplet ^3P excited states of $\text{Ag}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+}$ and $\text{Ag}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4^{2+}$ perturbed by water ligand field interaction. Blue arrows represent the allowed transitions while the green arrows represent the luminescent transitions between the relaxed states.

The key role of water ligands in AgCLs electronic properties is highlighted in the energy level diagram (Fig. 2B and Fig. S17) of $\text{Ag}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4^{2+}$ and $\text{Ag}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+}$ along with water-free Ag_4^{2+} clusters as reference. In water-free unperturbed Ag_4^{2+} , the ground state is the HOMO $^1\text{S}_0$ and the LUMOs consist of threefold degenerated singlet ^1P and triplet ^3P excited states. Upon coordination with water, the ligand field lifts the degeneracy of the LUMOs into six excited states, i.e., three singlet ^1P ($S = 0, L = 1, m_l = -1, +1$ or 0) and three triplet ^3P ($S = 1, L = 1, m_l = -1, +1$ or 0) states. The absorption occurs from the ground state corresponding to two electrons of opposite spins on a $^1\text{S}_0$ HOMO s-like orbital to the singlet excited states ^1P (3.5 and 3.7 eV) that correspond to one electron on a s-like orbital and one electron on LUMO, LUMO+1, LUMO+2 p-like orbitals with the two electrons having opposite spins.

These transitions feature large oscillator strengths f as they are allowed both by spin and angular momentum selection rules. The strong overlap of the high-energy triplet 3P ($S = 1, L = 1, m_l = 0$) state with the 1P singlet states ensures, in combination with large spin-orbit coupling expected for silver, an enhanced intersystem crossing. Upon light excitation, a fraction of 1P singlet states population is transferred to the high-energy triplet state that finally decays into the low-lying 3P ($S = 1, L = 1, m_l = -1$ or $+1$) triplet state. As shown in Fig. 2B, the intensity of the ligand-field splitting of the p-like LUMOs is directly proportional to the number of water molecules coordinating AgCLs, decreasing the band gap when going from $Ag_4(H_2O)_2^{2+}$ to $Ag_4(H_2O)_4^{2+}$ isomers. The bright green emission of $Ag_4(H_2O)_4^{2+}$ then occurs from the lowest-lying 3P triplet excited state 3P ($S = 1, L = 1, m_l = -1$) to the ground state 1S_0 .

The modeled absorption spectra for the $Ag_4(H_2O)_4^{2+}$ and $Ag_4(H_2O)_2^{2+}$ isomers (Fig. 3) are in excellent agreement with the steady-state optical experimental data. Calculated absorption peaks found at 343 and 320 nm in $Ag_4(H_2O)_4^{2+}$ and $Ag_4(H_2O)_2^{2+}$, respectively, closely match the experimental excitation peaks at 340 nm (3.64 eV) and 310 nm (4.00 eV). These results also confirm the assumption that the 37/63 intensity ratio of the two main emission peaks is directly related to the 34/66 fraction ratio of $Ag_4(H_2O)_4$ and $Ag_4(H_2O)_2$ present in Ag_3K_9 -LTA composites. Finally, the green PL energy obtained experimentally at 550 nm (2.25 eV) fits the transition energy of 556 nm (2.23 eV) of the modeled transition from the relaxed lowest-lying 3P triplet excited state to the 1S_0 ground state (Fig. 2B).

Fig. 3. Steady state excitation–emission of $\text{Ag}_3\text{K}_9\text{-LTA}$. Two-dimensional excitation–emission plot (A) and excitation spectrum $\lambda_{\text{detection}}=555$ nm of as-prepared $\text{Ag}_3\text{K}_9\text{-LTA}$ (B). The inset in the 2D plot shows the picture of an x-ray irradiated sample under 366 nm illumination. Calculated $^1\text{S}_0$ HOMO to $^1\text{P}(S = 0, L = 1, m_l = -1, +1)$ LUMOs absorption spectra of $x=2$ and $x=4$ $[\text{Ag}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_x]^{2+}$ isomers showing a good agreement with experiments.

To determine the decay time scale and energies of $\text{Ag}_3\text{K}_9\text{-LTA}$ modeled optical transitions and to verify the triplet nature of its bright green PL, we performed a global analysis of the decays obtained by femtosecond fluorescence up-conversion, time-correlated single-photon counting (TCSPC), and nanosecond luminescence time-resolved spectroscopies. Decays obtained by fs fluorescence up-conversion in the range 410 to 570 nm reveal three time components of 0.5 and 2.6 ps related to relaxation processes and >50 ps attributed to the ^1P to $^1\text{S}_0$ transition (Fig. 4, A and B, and Fig. S24 for decay traces, Table S5). The Amplitude-to-wavelength dependence (AWD) of the first two ultrafast components (maxima centered at 510 and 530 nm) are slightly blue shifted relative to the maximum of the steady-state emission spectrum (550 nm), suggesting the rapid depopulation of $^1\text{P}(S = 0, L = 1, m_l = -1, +1)$ singlet excited states. These ultrafast components attributed to non-fluorescent short-lived intermediate species formed after the relaxation of ^1P Franck-Condon states match closely the energy of the $^1\text{P}(S = 0, L = 1, m_l = -1)$ to $^1\text{S}_0$ transition predicted by TD-DFT (Fig. 4). These intermediate states rapidly convert into fluorescent ^3P triplet states lying at similar energies via intersystem crossing (Fig. 2B and 4, B and D).

Fig. 4. Time-resolved spectroscopy of $\text{Ag}_3\text{K}_9\text{-LTA}$. Amplitude-to-wavelength dependence (AWD) (A) and (B) 3D time-resolved fluorescence emission spectra in 50 ps time window obtained by fs fluorescence up-conversion C), in 1 ms time window by ns luminescence, (D) schematic illustration of the main electronic states involved.

This model is confirmed by the analysis of the PL decays in the micro- to millisecond range that reveal three time constants of 423 ns, 10.6 and 116 μs . Based on the AWD presented in Fig. 4C, the 423-ns component is attributed to an excited state with an intense emission peaking at 540 nm (2.30 eV) with estimated radiative and non-radiative rates of $5.43 \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $18.2 \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively. The close resemblance of the AWD of this state with the sample stationary emission spectrum indicates that these long-lived species are at the origin of the bright green emission observed in $\text{Ag}_3\text{K}_9\text{-LTA}$. This emission occurring from long-lived states that are characteristic for spin-forbidden transitions points toward their peculiar triplet nature. The other decay times of 10.6 and 118 μs we attribute to two different triplet excited states with weak emission centered at 630 and 680 nm (1.97 and 1.82 eV), respectively (Fig. 2B and Fig. S25 for decay traces, Table S6), associated to the presence of residual amounts of emissive species such as AgCPLs with different size and/or water coordination. (10)

The triplet nature of Ag₃K₉-LTA bright green emission is further corroborated by the significant enhancement of the PL accompanied by a dramatic increase of the decay time from 423 ns to 106 μs for the 540 nm main emission at low temperature (77K) while the faster components remained mostly unaffected (Fig. S26-S33). This result shows that excited-state kinetics, where non-radiative decay channels are hindered at low temperature and characteristic of triplet state emissions, is involved. Hence, the close correspondence between the computational and the photophysics results confirm that the bright PL of Ag₃K₉-LTA is occurring from the long-lived lowest-lying triplet excited state ³P(S = 1, L = 1, m_l = -1) of Ag₄(H₂O)₄ and Ag₄(H₂O)₂ clusters confined in the sodalite cages, rather than from a charge transfer process that was generally proposed for Ag zeolites in the absence of water ligands. (28-30) We anticipate that similar photophysical properties may also apply to photo-luminescent AgCLs confined in other scaffolds.

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Supplementary Materials References

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Supplementary Materials

Materials and Methods

Supplementary Text

Figs. S1 to S35

Tables S1 to S6